

Supplementary Figure 1: Plasma steroid profiles in CS, MACS, and NFAT patients

PLS-DA was performed to determine whether steroid profiles distinguished among the CS, MACS and NFAT groups. The numbers of patients are as follows: premenopausal women (CS, n = 4; MACS, n = 13; NFAT, n = 11), postmenopausal women (CS, n = 3; MACS, n = 21; NFAT, n = 32), and men (CS, n = 4; MACS, n = 19; NFAT, n = 34). Abbreviations: PLS-DA, partial least squares-discriminant analysis; CS, Cushing's syndrome ; ACS, autonomous cortisol secretion; NFAT, non-functioning adrenal tumors.

Supplementary Figure 2: Plasma steroid profiles in MACS and NFAT patients

PLS-DA was performed to determine whether steroid profiles distinguished between the MACS and NFAT groups. The numbers of patients are as follows: premenopausal women (MACS, n = 13; NFAT, n = 11), postmenopausal women (MACS, n = 21; NFAT, n = 32), and men (MACS, n = 19; NFAT, n = 34). Abbreviations: PLS-DA, partial least squares-discriminant analysis; ACS, autonomous cortisol secretion; NFAT, non-functioning adrenal tumors.

Supplementary Figure 3: Comparison of plasma AND-G levels between MACS and NFAT

Cohen's d values were calculated to compare AND-G between patients with MACS and NFAT. $p < 0.05$ are colored. The analysis was categorized into premenopausal women (MACS, $n = 13$; NFAT, $n = 11$), postmenopausal women (ACS, $n = 21$; NFAT, $n = 32$) and men (ACS, $n = 19$; NFAT, $n = 34$). Abbreviations: AND-G, androsterone-glucuronide; MACS, mild autonomous cortisol secretion; NFAT, non-functioning adrenal tumors.

Supplementary Figure 4: Correlation of AND-G with inflammatory markers and TBS in premenopausal women with MACS

We evaluated the correlation between AND-G and representative inflammatory markers (PNI and SII) (A) and TBS (B) in premenopausal women with MACS ($n = 13$). $p < 0.05$ are colored. Abbreviations: AND-G, androsterone-glucuronide; TBS, trabecular bone score; MACS, mild autonomous cortisol secretion; PNI, prognostic nutritional index; SII, systemic immune-inflammation index.

Supplementary Figure 5: Correlation of AND-G with inflammatory markers and TBS in premenopausal women with NFAT

We evaluated the correlation between AND-G and representative inflammatory markers (PNI and SII) (A) and TBS (B) in premenopausal women with NFAT (n = 11).

Abbreviations: AND-G, androsterone-glucuronide; TBS, trabecular bone score; NFAT, non-functioning adrenal tumors; PNI, prognostic nutritional index; SII, systemic immune-inflammation index.